

Evaluating hybrid seed production technology along with the new growth hormone Mangiferin

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Doubts have been raised about the economic viability of hybrid seed production as rice is predominantly a self-pollinated crop. An efficient seed production package is as important as improving cytotsterile lines and developing and evaluating hybrids. We attempted to evaluate hybrid seed production technology using the new growth hormone Mangiferin because the cost of gibberellic acid (GA_3) was high. Besides Mangiferin, glycine was also used to economize hybrid seed production in rice. Using GA_3 , boric acid, urea, Mangiferin, and glycine in different concentrations, we studied their effect on several characters in hybrids, such as duration of opening of florets, stigma exertion, angle of opened florets, plant height before and after spraying, panicle exertion at 5%, at 50% flowering, and at maturity, grain yield ha^{-1} , 1000-grain weight, and spikelet length. Analysis of variance showed highly significant differences for all the characters except panicle exertion at 50% flowering, which was significant only at 5%. In general, treatment combinations of GA_3 and Mangiferin produced a positive response for most floral and associated traits. GA_3 at 40-60 ppm or GA_3 +1.5% boric acid influenced more than one character: duration of opening of florets, stigma exertion, grain yield $plant^{-1}$, plant height, and panicle exertion. The treatment with GA_3 +1.5% boric acid was one of the most effective combinations as it influenced almost all the characters studied. Mangiferin in different combinations and concentrations also responded like GA_3 . Mangiferin alone (60 ppm) or in combination with boric acid influenced

many traits: duration of opening of florets, stigma exertion, angle of opened florets, grain yield ha^{-1} , plant height, and panicle exertion. All these traits recorded higher values than the control. The treatment containing GA_3 or Mangiferin (60 ppm) along with flag leaf clipping and rope pulling had much higher values for duration of opening of florets and stigma exertion than the control. Another important finding was the use of glycine in enhancing outcrossing in rice. GA_3 and glycine (40 ppm each) applied together resulted in 23% more yield than with the control. ■

Synchronization studies in hybrid rice seed production

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The two parents of a hybrid combination differ in their growth duration and therefore flower at different times even when sown on the same date. To produce hybrid seed successfully on a commercial scale, male and female parents planted side by side in a fixed row ratio should flower simultaneously, which is called synchronization. Synchronized flowering between two parental lines of different growth duration can be achieved by seeding them on different dates which is termed seeding interval (SI). The method of arriving at an SI using growth duration is simple to practice. In this method, the difference between parental lines in the number of days to initial heading or 50% flowering from seeding is used to determine SI. The growth duration of a variety, however, is known to be influenced by seasonal and weather conditions. Therefore, it is essential to determine an SI between the two parents of a hybrid for each season and location. The present study aimed at understanding the effect of different seeding dates in a season on growth duration

and its implications in hybrid seed production. The material consisted of 19 restorers belonging to different maturity groups—early (6), medium (5), and late (8)—and 3 cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines with their maintainers. All were sown on five different dates from 11 Jun 1994 at 5-d intervals. The seedlings were uprooted 30 d after sowing and planted in a randomized block design with three replications at a spacing of 20×15 cm. Observations on initial heading and days to 50% flowering were recorded for each entry and in each replication. The first and last sowings increased growth duration irrespective of the material used; the last sowing on 1 Jul increased growth duration by 5-8 d in restorers, 4 d in CMS lines, and 12 d in maintainers compared with the first sowing. Other sowings did not influence growth duration markedly.

The results clearly show that there is a definite time period for sowing within which growth duration is not affected significantly. Therefore, growth duration could safely be used to determine SIs to ensure synchronized flowering in parental lines. Studies should be conducted for a given hybrid combination at each seed production location and for each season. Seeding interval determined by growth duration would then become a much more reliable parameter for long-term use. ■

Effect of seedling age on flowering time in A, B, and R lines

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Flowering time in parental lines plays a vital role in hybrid rice seed production. Transplanting rice seedlings at the right age assumes special significance in obtaining higher yields in cultivation as well as in hybrid seed production. In